

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MUSAU****FIRST NAME: SARAH****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Knowledge claims are also known as research paradigms or schools of thought. Qualitative research is a broad approach to the study of social phenomena majorly based on two research paradigms. Which are they?**

- Constructivist and critical¹.**
- Postpositivist and pragmatic.
- Grounded theory and pragmatic.
- Postpositivist and phenomenology.

2. **Which are the MAIN instruments of data collection in qualitative research?**

- Interviews and surveys.

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg, and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 10.

- Observation, survey, interviews, documents, focus group, and critical incidents².**
- Observation, scales, ranking order checklists, interviews, and measurements.
- Ranking order checklists focus group discussions and survey.
3. **A research argument supports a working hypothesis. At the core of the research argument, there are three elements a researcher must observe. Which of the following answers is CORRECT?**
- Evidence, warrant, and citations.
- A question, an objection, and a warrant.
- A claim, a question, and a warrant.
- A claim, reasons for accepting it, and evidence that support those reasons³.**
4. **In scholarly writing, academic ethics is highly upheld through citations. Citations guard against plagiarism. There are three situations in which citations apply EXCEPT?**
- When you paraphrase ideas that are associated with a specific source, even if you do not quote exact words from it.
- When you use any idea, data, or method attributable to any source you consulted.
- When you categorically use your own words⁴.**

² Ibid., 14.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff (Chicago: The University of Chicago, 2013), 37.

- when you quote exact words from a source.
5. **An academic research proposal is a well-thought-out written action plan that identifies:**
- A problem statement, purpose statement, research questions, literature review, and data collection and data analysis methods⁵.**
- Introduction, an action plan, and data collection.
- An abstract, introduction, and an action plan.
- A table of content, introduction, and data collection.
6. **Within the qualitative approach, there are a variety of traditions or genres, each distinguished by a specific form, terms, focus, and assumptions regarding what constitutes inquiry within the qualitative paradigm. Which of the following traditions define qualitative research?**
- Experimental Research, Case Study, and Causal.
- Case Study, Grounded Theory, Ethnography, Hermeneutics, Narrative Inquiry, and Phenomenology⁶.**
- Narrative, Experimental, and Causal.
- Grounded Theory, Critical Theory, and Pragmatic.
7. **Based on the ACA-401D course pack, in academic writing, some changes are permissible within a quotation. When do these changes apply?**

⁴ Ibid., 86.

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation*, 17.

⁶ Ibid., 10, 13.

- Only when you want to add emphasis.
- Only on journal articles.
- Added words, added emphasis, foreign language, and citation in the original word⁷.**
- Added emphasis, foreign language and in biblical texts.

8. **In scholarly writing, usually, when are ellipsis points NOT used?**

- After a comma or a semicolon.
- When there is a question or exclamation mark.
- Before a conjunction or an independent clause.
- Before the first word of a quotation, even if the beginning of the original sentence has been omitted; or after the last word of a quotation, even if the end of the original sentence has been omitted, unless the sentence as quoted [in the original] is deliberately incomplete⁸.**

9. **According to the European Commission Style Guide, what is the difference between contractions and truncations?**

- Contractions shorten the word while truncations state the word in full.
- Contractions omit the middle of a word and are not followed by a period while truncations omit the end of a word and sometimes other letters as well and end in a point⁹.**

⁷ EUCLID, *ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 48.

⁸ Ibid., 49.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (2011), 27.

- Contractions omit the end of a word while truncations omit the middle of a word.
- Truncations are applied only in the European Commission while contractions are widely used across the academic community.

10. **In qualitative research, interview is the most used instrument of data collection. In a reference list, how should unpublished interview be cited?**

- Name of the interviewer, date, name of the interviewee, and location.
- Name of the interviewee, date, name of the interviewer, place and specific day of the interview (if known) and the location of any tapes or transcripts¹⁰.**
- Name of the interviewer, date, and place of interview.
- Name of the interviewee, date and location of the interview.

¹⁰ Turabian, Manual for Writers, 150.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 2011.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

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